

Elders learning English for Europe

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SITUATED LEARNING METHODOLOGY

Elders Learning English for Europe

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

INTRODUCTION.....	6
SITUATED LEARNING	7
Theoretical background of the Situated Learning: Reformpädagogik	7
Situated learning today	8
The role of the teacher/mentor/facilitator	9
Why to choose situated learning?	11
Situated Learning in comparison to other alternative methods	11
METHODS OF APPLYING SITUATED LEARNING	13
Group Activities.....	13
Role Play	13
Scenario-Based Learning.....	13
Using Technology	13
LANGUAGE TEACHING	15
Forms of Situated Language Learning	16
Communities of practice (cop):	16
Online language learning communities:	16
Authentic language learning:	16
Task-based language learning:.....	16
Virtual language learning (VLL):.....	16
Cognitive apprenticeship model:	17
Dramatization:	17
PRINCIPLES OF SITUATED LEARNING FOR MEANINGFUL LEARNING.....	18
Memory.....	18
Comprehension/Understanding.....	18
Applying	19
Generating/Creating.....	19
Assessment	20
COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE TEACHING	20
Authentic Materials	21
The role of the body in Situated learning.....	21
Situated Learning and Classroom Teaching.....	22

Using technology to support situated learning	23
For the creation of authentic learning activities or tasks	23
For support or scaffold	23
For reflective activities	23
Modelling	24
Coaching	24
Articulation.....	24
Reflection.....	25
STUDIES ON SITUATED LEARNING.....	26
Study at the School of Tourism in Erzincan University	26
Study by Marta García-Sampedro.....	26
Critics on Constructivist-oriented Teaching and Learning Concepts.....	27
SITUATED LEARNING IN TEACHING ENGLISH TO SENIORS	29
Bingo talks	29
Scavenger Hunt Reading	30
Class blog	30
Take a survey	30
EXAMPLE OF GOOD PRACTICE IN USING SITUATED LEARNING FOR TEACHING ENGLISH TO SENIORS	31
Slovenia: University for third Age Rogaška Slatina.....	31
Poland: Instytut Badan i Innowacji w Edukacji.....	32
Spain: Third Age Universities	37
Turkey: situated learning studies.....	38
Portugal: UTA movement in Portugal	40
REFERENCES.....	42

INTRODUCTION

People have begun to live longer, and their active life notions and activities have gone through changes. Greater life expectancy is an important issue that challenges countries around the globe. The ageing of populations affects all aspects of human life in social, financial, cultural, and political domains. One of the important issues of the 21st century is understanding and providing for ageing.

Currently, one out of every ten people is aged 60 or above. It is estimated that by 2050 one out of five people will be aged 60 or older. By 2150, one out of every three people is estimated to be 60 and over. With lower birth rates and higher life expectancy, the proportion of the elderly is already one in four in some developed countries (Erişen, 2010). According to the United Nations (UN), the 21st century will be the century of the old, which is also referred the “silver tsunami” (Boulton-Lewis, 2010).

The developing countries are also facing the reality of the ageing issue. Turkey is among the developing countries category and has a relatively younger population. However, having an ageing population has been on its agenda in recent years (Erişen, 2010) and the country is experiencing a new demographic structure. Starting from the year 2020, the proportion of this group of population is expected to be 20%, with an expected increase in the following years.

Active participation of elderly individuals in social life brings many advantages not only for them but also for the societies they live in. Various programs and projects around the world have investigated how and why elderly people should be involved in social life through active living. This project focuses on the learning of elderly individuals with a specific focus on learning English for travel purposes and presents findings obtained from the questionnaire administered for determining their needs on this issue.

SITUATED LEARNING

In the past, learning was believed to be developed in a stable, objective world, with no special emphasis being put on context and activities. At the same time traditional education stated that knowledge exists in people's heads, emphasizing the transmission of content into the people's minds. This traditional mind-set has been criticized a lot in the last years, especially by the experts addressing the area of learning and knowledge from a different, more modern point of view which sees learning as a process that occur from activity in a subjective and socially constructed world, claiming that only actively acquired knowledge enables an individual to develop a good understanding of the world and possibility to use his or her knowledge in various situations. The same experts also claim that learners often have no use of knowledge gained in educational organizations because educational settings and the real world are two very different things. (Rambusch, 2004).

The term Situated Learning was first proposed by Jean Lave and Etienne Wenger as a model of learning in a community of practice. They insisted that this kind of learning should not be considered as a simple transmission of abstract and decontextualized knowledge from one learner to another, but a social process during which knowledge is co-constructed. At the same time, this kind of learning should be put into a specific context within a particular social and physical environment (Efe, Demiröz and Akdemir, 2011).

Theoretical background of the Situated Learning: Reformpädagogik

If we take a closer look of theoretical background of the situated learning, we cannot go on without mentioning 'Reformpädagogik,' German educational movement, which criticized the so called 'book school' and promoted 'work school'.

The main promoter of this philosophy was Kerschensteiner, who vastly reorganized the primary and vocational school system and was the main influence on the German dual system in vocational education in Germany. He emphasized that manual work should be closely tied to mental work and introduced the kitchen and garden instruction in schools, where learners learned different subjects, such as chemistry, physics, physiology, and mathematics, based on authentic activities. In such way, the instructional questions did not come from the teachers, but from learners while they

were working on various problems that helped to reduce the gap between school and everyday life.

Later on, Kerschensteiner addressed the issue of whether school prepared learners for their professional lives, which led to the development of the German vocational training system, where the training at the workplace is closely linked to the teaching in the compulsory, part-time vocational school (Gruber and Mandl, 2001).

Many of the *Reformpädagogik* ideas were implemented in the situated learning movement under cognitive psychological and constructivist perspectives. We can identify 5 main instructional principles:

- Learning by solving authentic problems: here a problem is a starting point, acting as a motivation for learners and as a facilitator of putting the learning process in meaningful contexts and knowledge acquisition with the help of application and not abstract teaching;
- Multiple perspectives: elements are analysed from various perspectives and contexts that encourage multiple conditionalization which eliminates the emergence of dysfunctional oversimplifications and promotes active abstraction processes;
- Articulation and reflection: when learners externalize mental processes, they are able to compare their strategies with strategies coming from experts and other learners;
- Cooperative format: cooperative learning enables the comparison with experts and peer learners and acquiring these competences can be of great use in professional lives of the learners.
- Learning as enculturation: one of the goals of learning is to become enculturated into communities of practice. For this purpose, learners have to gain a sense of authentic practice, functional belief systems, ethical norms, and the tricks of the trade (Gruber and Mandl, 2001).

Situated learning today

The main goal of situated learning is for adults to learn by doing and on real-life situations that they can relate to. Therefore, this kind of learning is quite different from traditional learning where basically people are learning from the abstract. In order for situated learning to be successful, it should not be carried out in isolation but rather in groups where learners can debate and state their arguments to each other. The main emphasis of this kind of learning is to connect the content learned in a classroom to the knowledge required outside the classroom, which also means that this kind of learning is successful only when the learner can connect the content learned in a classroom to the real-life situations. In addition, learners produce their knowledge

through experience from the relationships and activities with other participants, the environmental cues, and the social organization of the community (A Research Guide, n. d.; Stein, n. d.).

If we want to understand situated learning, we must comprehend the situated view of knowledge:

To understand situated learning and work through its implications for instructional design, we must understand the situated view of knowledge:

- When using knowledge, individuals create information and new, personal representations that occur during every day activities;
- When people are taking actions, they are not following schemas, procedures or rules from their memory – they are constantly forming something new;
- Things that we see and do during the interaction result in forming new, coordinated compositions of perception and action, which shapes future behaviour (Clancey, 1995).

The role of the teacher/mentor/facilitator

According to Young's research from 1993, mentors should bear in mind 4 important tasks while implementing situated learning in adult classrooms:

- First of all, they should choose situations that will involve learners in realistic, problem-focused, and comprehensive situations that will stimulate the acquirement of new knowledge.
- Secondly, mentors should provide the basis for new learners and therefore be familiar with the amount of guidance that learners need to master different situations. Naturally, they will need more guidance at the beginning and less once they start gaining additional knowledge and skills.
- In addition, mentors gradually change their roles from transmitting the content to facilitating learning with the help of monitoring progress and products made by learners while they build collaborative learning environments, promote reflection, and help learners in becoming more conscious of contextual clues that can help with their understanding.
- Lastly, mentors should constantly evaluate the intellectual growth of their learners and at the same time, they can use the cognitive apprenticeships where learners can see how mentors solve problems that help them develop their own paths of solving problems (Stein, n. d.).

In the classroom where situated learning takes place, the teacher/mentor/facilitator plays a very important role as he/she offers the following:

- Coaching and observing learners at critical times while offering support to learners who cannot carry out the tasks
- Hints and reminders
- Feedbacks
- Modelling

When learners gain more knowledge and become more proficient, the mentor can slowly start giving less support and then his/her main task becomes to move the learners towards self-directed learning and afterwards towards generalizing or transferring the skills. The mentor helps learners to achieve better understanding of activities and get more positive outcomes. After gaining more control and self-confidence, learners take over a more autonomous phase of collaborative learning and conscious participation in the culture (Hajah Siti Norainna Binti Pengiran Haji Besar, 2018).

In 1996, McLellan also noted that the key components of situated learning model are:

- Stories
- Reflection
- Cognitive apprenticeship
- Collaboration
- Coaching
- Multiple practice
- Articulation of learning skills
- Technology (Efe, Demiröz and Akdemir, 2011).

When designing classes with situated learning, the mentor has to bear in mind the followings:

- Learning is more efficient when learners are faced with a problem themselves and have to think about it and act on it as experts. It is important to note that problems need to be realistic and relevant to the situation presented.
- The mentor does not act as a lecturer but as a coach and a model who divides information into smaller that which will help learners to solve problems;
- The learning environment has to be set up in such way that it encourages learners to reflect, discuss and evaluate thinking while learners are actively engaged in a situation;
- The mentor does not teach the content of the course; participants learn through real-life and contextual activities (Kurt, 2021).

Why to choose situated learning?

A review of different literature by different experts, educators and scientists indicates several reasons for choosing situated learning, which includes the followings:

- It provides increased attention and learning motivation of learners;
- It is based on learners' social capacities;
- It encourages the development and improvement of communicative and pragmatic language competencies;
- It forms a meaningful language learning environment;
- It includes creativity into the traditional language learning process;
- It encourages a positive and interactive language learning atmosphere;
- It connects language learning theories and actual practices (theory and practice);
- It strengthens a contextualised acquisition of new language segments (vocabulary, structure);
- It shows how to use linguistic forms and structures in real-life situations;
- It helps to make learners more relaxed during the learning process;
- It broadens learners' horizons;
- It makes language learning more fun and enjoyable;
- It makes the language learning process a contextualized process;
- Learners can understand learning goals and objectives easier;
- Learners can easily share and employ their linguistic input;
- It promotes the use of digital tools and social media in meaningful language practices;
- It reinforces reflection of learners on their own learning, and it attracts their attention (Abdallah, M. M. S. (2015).

Situated Learning in comparison to other alternative methods

In the last decades, many alternative approaches in education have emerged, including methods by Montessori, Waldorf, Pestalozzi and Rousseau. The mentioned theories have a few similar points about learning and knowledge with situated learning theory:

- They are against the teaching approach where the learner is a passive recipient and not active participant;
- They do not consider learning and knowledge acquisition as a process where ready-made knowledge is transferred from one individual to another, but rather describe the processes of learning and education as an individual and social activity in a rich learning environment.

However, there are also differences between alternative methods and situated learning:

- The advocates of Montessori and Waldorf education claim that an individual goes through various developmental stages through their progress in life, while the advocates of situated learning method are not bothered by this, emphasizing socio-cultural aspects such as mediated activity and the social environment of learning occurs;
- Montessori, Pestalozzi or Waldorf methods state that learners and their needs are the starting point of each scientific discussion, while situated learning approach focuses on sincere interest in how learners learn and what the characteristic of knowledge is (Rambusch, 2004);

We can say that alternative approaches and situated learning theories have more differences than similarities, most of them deriving from disagreements about the dualistic perspective and partly contradicting research interests.

METHODS OF APPLYING SITUATED LEARNING

There are different methods to apply Situated learning, which include group activities, role-plays, scenario-based learning, and using technology.

Group Activities

A very good way to involve learners in group activities is field trips where they can actively take action in an unfamiliar environment and gain knowledge and skills from practical experience. Another idea is to create different real-life situations in the classroom, and create imaginative hotels, restaurants, administrative facilities, etc. where learners are involved in problem solving activities that replicate real-life settings (Origin Learning, 2015).

Role Play

Here learning occurs through the actions from everyday situations where learners play certain roles – tourist at a restaurant or at a hotel, customer in a shop or a bank, etc. For this reason, it is crucial to indulge learners in such role-play situations that will involve them in comprehensive, realistic, and problem-centered activities, and the mentor should provide help in gaining the desired knowledge. Knowledge is gained contextually and is transferred only to similar situations. Therefore, the mentor should not be a teacher but rather a facilitator. Another important thing here is to track and assess the progress of the learners, encourage reflections, and help them to become more aware of contextual hints and build collaborative learning environments (Origin Learning, 2015; Ochoa, Gómez-Ullate, Herman, 2015).

Scenario-Based Learning

Here learning is based on complex social environments consisting of actions, actors, and situations. Mentors provide scenarios for learners and offer them the right amount of help to cope with various situations. Naturally, the amount of support needed will decrease as learners gain additional skills and knowledge. The assessment of learners' intellectual growth is of crucial importance, which can be reached through discussion, reflection and evaluation (Origin Learning, 2015).

Using Technology

When learners learn through a game or through social media, information and facts can be explained effortlessly. Using social networks, such as Facebook, Twitter or Instagram enables learners to become a part of a new community where they can learn

from each other. They can use social networks for creating social interactions which can play a significant role in the learning process (Origin Learning, 2015).

LANGUAGE TEACHING

Language teaching occurs in various settings and is influenced by many factors. In 1987, Malamah – Thomas stated that setting has three levels in an educational system: the country, the school and the classroom. This raises the question of the relationship between the role of English in the country and teaching it at school. It is clear that using and hearing the language in the environment is just as important as teaching English at school (Efe, Demiröz and Akdemir, 2011).

The main purpose of learning a foreign language is to communicate with each other. To achieve this, one must understand the language he is using, and speaking is one of the basic skills and tools of expressing our feelings, ideas, beliefs and information. Reading and writing are also important for promoting eloquence and comprehension, yet speaking takes over the most important role in communication (Tawil, 2018).

Teaching a foreign language contains a complex structure. Creating the best possible effect, it should achieve optimal values in the following four conditions: proximity to spoken language, equality of four skills, internal and external interferences of the learner, and teaching and learning materials. For learners of foreign languages, the most efficient way is to learn in a learning environment of real communication and performance, especially while being exposed to spoken language and cultural elements of a foreign language (Efe, Demiröz and Akdemir, 2011). In addition, when learners use language as a case in point, they learn the targeted language through conversation and interaction with other people, as well as through exposure to visual stimuli. This creates an immersed environment where learners are exposed to a vast variety of factors which influence learners' speech (Romaniuk, 2018).

Authentic situations we encounter outside lecture halls are extremely efficient for learners. Therefore, it is important they are exposed to language as much as possible, including outside the school environment. They should also be given appropriate tools and tasks that require interaction with real people so that they can learn the language outside school. For example, if you teach English language, encourage them to visit law a typical English pub or come in contact with anything that is English (4 elements, n. d.).

If we want to communicate well in a foreign language, we need to know grammar and vocabulary which we achieve by learning four skills: reading, writing, speaking, listening and learning about the culture behind a foreign language. Interaction in a foreign language means that we form sentences that are grammatically correct, it also means internalizing the cultural code, values and ways of thinking and acting (4 elements, n. d.).

On the other hand, in 2008 David stated that a learner can have a great knowledge of vocabulary and grammar but he or she is not able to use it in practical applications and conversations. David claims this happens because of the gap between correct grammar and correct meaning and since speech is used in social situations, the language loses its functionality and importance. In 2015, Abdallah and Mansour also showed that speaker with basic knowledge of vocabulary and syntax mostly speak meaninglessly (Tawil, 2018).

Forms of Situated Language Learning

There are several forms of teaching-learning situations in situated learning:

Communities of practice (cop):

This form involves a group of learners with common interests, goals, orientations and needs who communicate interactively in a form of social community to gain certain language learning goals and purposes.

Online language learning communities:

To overcome physical boundaries, the communities are connected through the Internet or the Web where they exchange language learning ideas, materials, experiences and facilities online (Marzano, Ochoa, 2017).

Authentic language learning:

In 1999, Nunan defined authentic materials as spoken or written language data produced during genuine communication, not for language teaching. Similar definition was already used earlier by Rogers and Medley, who defined this sort of material as samples reflecting a naturalness of form and an appropriateness of cultural and situational context found in language used by native speakers of the language.

Task-based language learning:

The tasks carried out by learners are the basis of the learning process. The teacher develops classroom activities around practical tasks that learners will be involved in the real-life situations. The tasks need to be authentic, interactive, situated, and goal oriented.

Virtual language learning (VLL):

3D Virtual Environments or MUVES are used as tools for foreign language instruction. They encourage collaboration and social presence in a realistic 3-D environment where learners can communicate with each other without any limits. Each learner has his/her own avatar that moves, walks, flies and socializes in their name, which enables

copying real-life situations in virtual environment and simulation of situations that would encourage functional and pragmatic use of the language learnt.

Cognitive apprenticeship model:

The teacher is approached as a person who masters a skill and teaches it to his or her learner. The goal is to capture the implicit processes while carrying out complex skills during instruction to beginners.

Dramatization:

Using drama for language teaching is perfect if you want your learners to learn in a more active and realistic way. With dramatization, teachers can transform the artificial world of the classroom into somewhat real language learning situations. Role-playing has the potential to transform passive learners into active participants. It also encourages learners to develop their communicative skills in authentic situations. (Abdallah, 2015).

PRINCIPLES OF SITUATED LEARNING FOR MEANINGFUL LEARNING

The most important focus of situated learning is to get learners involved and bring them from being just spectators of learning to the point where they become an active part of learning.

To achieve this, learners should work on problems with each other, while being supervised and guided by a mentor, who is constantly developing activities that expose learners to various stimuli, formulating problem-solving strategies and solutions with the help of personal and team collaboration. This enables learners to apply their logical skills and problem-solving skills that make them more engaged.

Activities can be formed according to the 5 principles connected to situated or cognitive learning: remembering, understanding, applying, evaluating, and creating.

Let's take a closer look at them:

Memory

If we immerse learners into various subjects, issues or topics, we encourage their cognitive processes and executive functions, such as memory operations, critical thinking, attention, visual, spatial, emotional and attention processes, problem solving and decision-making abilities, etc.

To achieve all of the above, teachers can use spontaneous quizzes that help learners recall crucial information from their memory. Learners can be asked to label maps, construct timelines, recall and note down quotes, write short bios, or retell one historical event (Romaniuk, 2018).

Comprehension/Understanding

When learners demonstrate their understanding of a topic in a classroom, this is a huge step forward in the field of integration of various resources and cognitive processes into the meaningfulness of learning. Teachers can ask their learners to show their comprehension of the simplicity or complexity of a chosen topic that encourages

them to use their analytical skills. While demonstrating their comprehension skills, learners train their memory recall.

Carrying out this sort of activities also stimulates sounds and images in learners' memories and motivates them to envision data in various forms, arranging them mentally before they pass their ideas or reactions to the issues posed in the classroom.

Teachers can use discussion forums where they ask learners to comment on various questions or short quotes. They can also create short debates in the classroom which help learners a good drill of their comprehension skills. A very good method is also the method of flipping a scenario where mentor presents an event or historical currents and invite learners to find outcomes of the scenarios or precursors to them (Romaniuk, 2018).

Applying

When learners apply their knowledge, this stimulates and implies creativity. When they are asked to apply their knowledge, learners use an entire set of cognitive skills, which reinforces the development of one another.

Teachers can encourage this activity by asking learners to speak about their favourite book or a movie in the classrooms. This will enable them to choose freely to apply what they know, on their own terms inside their comfort zones. In this way, learners have more time to speak in a targeted language, which gets them more involved and invokes the active dimensions of learners' engagement, which can be much more interesting than just the teachers speaking all the time. Teachers can even use learners' presentations to discuss certain concepts and definitions, which can be a starting point for explanation of theoretical concepts.

If teachers really want to stir up the atmosphere in the classroom, they can try games, where learners are exposed to descriptions of situations that are either contradictory in character or establish various puzzles or challenges. This exercise will for sure leave no learners in the classroom cold-blooded (Romaniuk, 2018).

Generating/Creating

Exposing learners to new and unexpected settings, stimuli and conditions, creates better versions of them, since they are getting to know their own natural skills they did not even know they possessed.

One very fun activity can be asking learners to write an alternative history to an event or come up with a different outcome of a famous historical event. This simple task can

encourage them to be very creative and will push their learning boundaries. Another good idea is for the teacher to ask learners to write down expected outcomes of a current event (Romaniuk, 2018).

Assessment

This activity involves learners into evaluating situations or case studies through a comparative approach. When learners are examining and analysing information, this encourages the use of long and short-term memory. They weigh these pieces of information against current topics addressed in the classrooms, bearing in mind syllabus and project outcomes. Learners can be asked to present their findings in different ways, which could encourage them to use various analysis and visualization methods.

Setting up focus groups in the classroom can also encourage constructive engagement and at the same time learners get to know methods in the social sciences. Teacher can ask learners to extract crucial points from a discussion and participate in a short assessment. A good method would also be to ask learners to weigh the benefits and pitfalls of certain decisions made throughout the history in the area of politics or international relations, which could stimulate learners to make judgements related to studies while using research strategies and approaches (Romaniuk, 2018).

COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE TEACHING

When our goal is for learners to learn a language in order to communicate, we come across the term Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) approach. It is based on communicative competence, which is described as the knowledge needed to be able to communicate effectively (Thornbury, 2006).

CLT aims broadly to apply the theoretical perspective of Communicative Approach (CA) by making communicative competence as the goal of language teaching and by acknowledging the interdependence of language and communication (Larsen – Freeman, 2008).

In a CLT design, language functions are emphasized rather than forms and grammatical patterns of a language. All four language skills are studied to have a meaningful competence of language. Besides, CLT is generally associated with notional – functional syllabuses (Larsen – Freeman, 2008).

Many educators and researchers who work in the field of language learning claim that successful learning can only come from collaboration, cognitive apprenticeship, and

situated cognition. Combining this, we will create a deep understanding and meaningful learning.

Various experts also claim that the most efficient way to learn a language is to take part in a community which uses the language one is learning to communicate in real life context. Taking part in this environment, learners have no place to hide and are forced to speak, think and write in the language they are trying to learn. This enables an environment with a natural and meaningful context where they can learn the desired language spontaneously.

When learning a foreign language in a situated learning environment, learners are active constructors of knowledge who include their own strategies, styles and needs to learning, and researches show that knowledge and skills are gained best when they are set in realistic contexts and authentic settings where learners carry out experiential language learning (Abdallah, 2015).

Authentic Materials

They are educational materials that educators use to teach natural and authentic competences, abilities and knowledge and are formed in a way to reflect the spoken language to learners.

When learning with authentic materials, learners can hear original dialogs of spoken language, learn about cultural patterns of a certain language and the change in the language, and find out about the daily news concerning the societies that speak the language. In addition, these materials are prepared easily and can be used in educational settings.

We divide authentic materials into written, visual and audio-visual materials.

A good example of written materials are sketches used to create a sketch dialogue, which helps to create an authentic language atmosphere and reflection of various language patterns. They enable overview of cultural characteristics, simplification, and appropriateness to the context (Efe, Demiröz and Akdemir, 2011).

The role of the body in Situated learning

Situated learning is defined as gaining of knowledge in a social context, which is strongly linked to bodily activity in a community of practice in terms of social interactions and usage of various tools. The role of the body refers to bodily activity in connection to tools and other participants in the learning environment.

Situated learning gives great emphasis on the interactions between teachers and learners since they are always trying to find ways to communicate with each other and understand each other. Here the combination of social stimuli and body conditions play a great role in the classroom. For example, if a teacher possesses a body posture that shows lack of motivation, this could have a negative impact on the learner's success and performance. On the other hand, a teacher that expresses a 'positive', happy body posture can have a very positive effect on his or her learners (Rambusch, 2004).

Situated Learning and Classroom Teaching

Situated learning should give learners the possibility to show their abilities and talents. Besides, it should create a learning environment that mirrors the tools and the culture used in real life situations. The mentor should consider how learners' participations in the classroom environment show their potential and abilities they have gained through the learning experience with social resources.

To create all this, mentors usually use various activities and tools which help create an artificial simulation of social contexts in the school environment.

One of these tools can for example be social media, such as Facebook, which can be used as an online space for collaborative activities (Ochoa, Marzano, Kaczmarczyk, 2017). Mentors can also use Weebly, which enables them to adopt their classrooms and teaching identities for designing websites with blogs, images, videos and imagined showcases of the future work of their learners. Facebook and Twitter can also be useful for involving learners in communication, sharing of content and collaboration. These social networks can be used as online classrooms for creating social interactions, building communities and relationships inside and outside the classroom environment where learners can discuss, share information, opinions and ideas. In 1998 Sfard, a great supporter of situated learning, stated that the possibility to participate encourages the sense of collaboration, solidarity and togetherness and promotes positive risk-taking in learning settings, which encourages learners towards further collaboration in the classroom (Ochoa, Herman, Marzano, 2015).

Situated learning also helps to prevent labelling of people since all options are open for learners, regardless of their histories of failure, which promotes learners' growth and progress, meaning one day you can act one way and tomorrow differently. Teamwork, where learners can help each other, also has many benefits for weaker learners and encourages them to contribute more, develop new understandings and gain knowledge by experiencing and taking part in real life situations (Hajah Siti Norainna binti Pengiran Haji Besar, 2018).

Using technology to support situated learning

If we want to stimulate learning with a situated context, we basically need to create a situated learning environment. Naturally, there are many ways to do this, but in recent years, especially during the Covid-19, technology has become one of the most important tools for creating a situated learning environment. Multimedia, including sounds, graphics, animations and digital videos can help in creating a believable real world context.

Since there are numerous technologies, teachers can use to create a situated learning environment; it is sometimes difficult to choose the right ones.

Here are some of the guidelines that teachers can use for choosing the right type of technology tools according to the topics or questions they wish to address:

For the creation of authentic learning activities or tasks

Here teachers should ask themselves about the real-world tasks which would demand application of the skill/knowledge and how these tasks could be introduced in a clear and interesting at the same time challenging for learners.

The technology tools they could use here are graphics, videos, interactive activities, animations and simulations.

For support or scaffold

Here teachers should ask themselves about the obtained knowledge of learners, the sequence of the learning activities, about the learning support learners need to compete the tasks successfully and in what way technology could help them with this and also consider the resources learners need to fulfil the set tasks.

The technology tools they could use here are videos, simulations and online interactive activities.

For reflective activities

the questions to be asked here are about how learners can know if they have learnt well and which activities could be formed in order to help learners master general principles that they could apply to other similar situations.

The technology tools they could use here are interactive activities (Bee Ling and Choo, 2005).

When creating situated learning environment using technology, teachers should consider 6 stages which will help them create authentic online tasks that teach complex processes or concepts:

Modelling

This stage should contain clear instructions that will help learners deal with the task. This could for example be achieved by creating a virtual presentation including all the steps needed to finish the task.

Coaching

Here learners are allowed to complete the online task themselves, while the mentor supervises the online task and gives learners feedback which assist learners to improve their approach or take a look at a problem from a different point of view. Giving feedback is very important because it enables learners to learn what they did incorrectly and helps them in moving forward.

Scaffolding

While modelling and coaching set the basis for learning, scaffolding gives learners the tools needed to build their mastery of the task. Scaffolding involves activities such as online group collaboration exercises, scenarios, and other supplemental online resources. Teachers can provide their learners with different links to suitable articles, videos, and webinars. At the same time, feedback coming from peers or mentor's assistance can be very helpful tools for learners who are struggling in carrying out the tasks and fill out the gaps.

Articulation

This stage is formed by three methodologies:

Inquiry: a method introduced by Collins and Stevens in 1982 in which mentor is asking a set of questions which encourages learners to examine and refine their answers in correlation to a certain conceptual idea or model;

Thinking aloud where learners try to articulate their thoughts while they are solving a problem; in certain cases, they can also be asked to observe groups and come up with their own conclusions based on activities and conversations;

Separation: learners need to separate the skills and the knowledge from the tasks because this is the only way they can investigate them at length; afterwards, they are encouraged to demonstrate and put into words what they have learned with the help of the analysis of their thinking process.

Reflection

In this stage learners compare their work among each other, peers and mentors. This stage might include self-analysis, peer feedback, or performance evaluations. Teachers can also provide more interactive reflection exercises, for example video presentations containing two individuals executing the same task, while teacher asks learners to contrast and compare them.

Exploration

This is the final stage where learners get the opportunity to investigate the task autonomously. Mentors should gradually take away all scaffolding resources so that learners can complete the building process on their own. Here learners try to carry out the task without any help from the peers or mentors. They use the gained knowledge and experience to overcome different challenges (Pappas, 2015).

STUDIES ON SITUATED LEARNING

Study at the School of Tourism in Erzincaan University

An experimental study for reviewing the role and efficiency of the situational learning approach was conducted at the School of Tourism in Erzincaan University, including 12 male and 11 female learners in the control group and 14 male and 10 female learners in the experimental group.

Before starting the study, they tested the language levels of learners with a language proficiency exam which mostly included dialogues. Afterward, they started with 8-week-lectures where learners in the experimental group were using authentic sketches for learning English. Learners in the control group used classical reading materials, which was followed by the same language proficiency test as the post-test.

The evaluations of pre and post-tests showed a huge difference in results of learners in the experimental group in comparison to learners from the control group, showing greater progress with the learners from the experimental group. These findings show that spoken language can be improved by authentic sketches designed to serve as a situated learning setting (Efe, Demiröz and Akdemir, 2011).

Study by Marta García-Sampedro

In 2018, Marta García-Sampedro published an interesting article titled »Cultural Heritage as a Resource for English as an Additional Language Learner: An Out-of-Class Approach« where she presented an interesting method of teaching English in informal places such as museums, art galleries, parks or historical buildings. The project was led by the Department of Educational Studies at the University of Oviedo, and its main goal was to increase the level of complexity of oral communication of learners in English, to learn about the school environment and cultural heritage in their area, to develop a penchant for cultural heritage and learn to appreciate the arts, while improving the motivation to learn in both learners and teachers. The results show an increase in the level of motivation of both learners and teachers due to the use of non-formal learning spaces and elements of cultural heritage as sources of learning (4 elements, n. d.).

Critics on Constructivist-oriented Teaching and Learning Concepts

Many studies are being done on the effects of situated learning, but experts claim that the findings are still not sufficient.

Several findings of transfer research contradict the claims of constructivist, who claim that knowledge is tied to context. The main problem is that learning according to constructivist principles ended in poorer results in subsequent knowledge tests. On the other hand, these findings can be questioned since some researches showed positive influence of situated learning according to the tests of the learners which were applied later on.

There have also been a lot critics claiming that teachers cannot pass along an objective reality to their learners, although the supporters of situated learning claim that it is possible to stimulate learning processes externally.

Another critique is that when using situated learning, teachers are given a lot of freedom, which often causes a big problem in making the right choices. Besides, the concepts such as activity and situation are very vague and the situated learning approach can be very time-consuming for teachers and learners.

Because of the lack of the support and directions offered to learners, situated learning can cause undesirable results, such as placing the demands to learners too high, especially when it comes to learners with disadvantageous learning conditions. The fact is that more motivated learners have more benefits from the situated learning as less motivated learners (Mandl and Reinmann-Rothmeier, 2001).

In 2001 Fenwick claimed that the supporters of situated learning ignore issues of gender, race, class and other personal and cultural issues. Learners have different abilities and not all of them will be able to participate meaningfully in certain systems of practice. In addition, he claimed that the situative perspective does not address the issues of resistance in communities, where activities and tools used can be unfair or even dysfunctional.

In 2003, Hooks, in her work *Teaching Community: A Pedagogy of Hope* addresses the issue of racism, stated that the lives of her learners continued to be affected by racial differences, although some researches have diminished her claim. She later on gave an example: she often spoke to her learners who usually claimed that racism has no effect on their lives, but when she gave them an exercise a minute later telling them they were about to die and they have to choose if they would come back as a white male or female or a black male or female. The results were stunning, since most of the learners, regardless their race or gender, chose male whiteness, while black females were chosen the least often. When she asked her learners to explain their choices,

they mostly mentioned privileges based on race and gender. Therefore, situated learning method should take into account that differences among learners will affect the bonding of a group.

Besides, we should also address the artificial activities and tools that teachers use for forming realistic situations. The fact is that activities taking place in a classroom can only simulate reality. If learners try to role play, one acting as a teacher and the other as a pupil, this will create a controlled situation and not a real life situation. Therefore, many experts claim that activities of learners in classroom cannot be the activities of practitioners.

In addition, some experts claim that the so called “hybrid activity” sets limits to learners when they want to access significant structuring and supporting cues from authentic contexts. Therefore, learners can get a completely false picture about what practitioners really do.

This was also mentioned by Contu and Willmott in 2003; they stated that situated learning caused problems by emphasizing the idea of “naturalness”.

Some critics have pointed out that learning in communities is not always the best choice, since there are learners without supervision learning in authentic environments where their involvement could strengthen negative practices which community is striving to eliminate. At the same time, experts claim that people who are trained in certain ways can take over undesirable shapes of practice and wrong values, which can limit the collectivity of participants. Such case would also be Facebook. According to some experts, although social network has various benefits, it still possesses different limitations during the learning processes, for example error corrections without clarification (Hajah Siti Norainna binti Pengiran Haji Besar, 2018).

SITUATED LEARNING IN TEACHING ENGLISH TO SENIORS

Percentage of seniors learning English as a foreign language is increasing more and more. Reasons for learning English in the third period of life can be different: children and grandchildren marrying foreign citizens, love for travelling, fight against memory loss and dementia, finding free-time activities, and so on.

Whatever the reason for studying English is, the fact is that teaching English to seniors can be rather different than teaching children or younger adults. Some scientists, such as Morandi, point out that older people tend to remember old memories better than recent facts, while Abrisqueta-Gomez states that elderly are prone to decline in processing speed, their resources in memory processing are reduced, they have inhibitory deficits related to the age, and decrease in cognitive control. Besides all of the factors mentioned, additional factors such as self-esteem, anxiety, stress and depression should be taken into consideration (Romário Monticelli Garcia, 2017).

Therefore, mentors teaching English as a second language to seniors should be very careful and should conduct English lessons in consideration of their needs . Creating a situated learning environment could of course be one of the right methods to choose, and here are some examples of designing an English class for seniors using the situated learning method:

Bingo talks

Mentor uses the board to write down some topics that learners are interested in and asks them to do short brainstorming activity and find key words in connection to each topic. Afterwards, the mentor draws u bingo cards with 9 spaces on each card. Learners are asked to choose and arrange words on their cards to listen for during someone else's short talk. One senior is asked to talk about a chosen topic using the words given. Other learners listen and try to find the words he or she uses on their bingo cards. When he or she finishes, other learner can start. Doing the exercises like this keeps learners really motivated and attentive because they have to listen carefully, and at the same time the given words help learners to make up sentences (FluentU, 2022).

Scavenger Hunt Reading

Here, to make topics more interesting, you can use local newspapers. The mentor prepares certain questions according to articles in the newspaper and asks learners to find answers for these questions in the newspaper. The questions and answer should of course be in English, while the newspaper should be in learners' native language. In this way, learners will train their language skills while processing real-life information from the local environment (FluentU, 2022).

Class blog

The mentor can create a class blog including an up-to-date affair. He or she asks learners to contribute their thoughts on the topic. The mentor, nevertheless, should also stress that communication in the blog should be respectful and not demeaning or hostile (FluentU, 2022).

Take a survey

A very good exercise to practice formation of questions as well as giving answers, while using interesting and up-to-date topics. Mentor can place learner into pairs or in groups and ask learners to choose a current topic they are interested in. After each pair or group chooses a topic, the mentor asks them to write a short survey on the topic to be able to find out what the point of view of other learners on this topic are. After they finish with the survey, the mentor discusses the questions they have created, and potential mistakes in the structures of the survey are eliminated. Later on, pairs or groups exchange the surveys and give answers to the surveys. At the end of the class, the results are analysed and discussed in the class (FluentU, 2022).

EXAMPLE OF GOOD PRACTICE IN USING SITUATED LEARNING FOR TEACHING ENGLISH TO SENIORS

Slovenia: University for third Age Rogaška Slatina

Runs under Ljudska univerza Rogaška Slatina, adult educational centre from Rogaška Slatina, Slovenia, started offering English courses for seniors in 2011. The same year, the mentor of the course together with the senior members of one of the English group came up with the idea to organize an end-of-the year excursion to London where senior learners could try out their gained knowledge of English in practice. Ever since that year, these end-of-the year excursions have become a tradition at the organization, now including all senior learners, not just participants of English courses.

In 2013, the mentor and senior learners came up with the idea to visit Ireland. While checking the prices of the trip at tourist agencies, the mentor soon realized that it would be much cheaper to organize the trip on her own. The main problem she was faced with was the fact that all of the sightseeing activities would be done by local guides who spoke a strong Irish dialect and her fear was that seniors, with different levels of knowledge of English language, would not understand the majority of the things spoken.

Therefore, at the beginning of the school year, she presented an idea to the most advanced group of senior learners of English. They took a look at the sights in Ireland where they would like to visit. After the list was created, the mentor told learners to choose one of the sights on the list. She explained that every two weeks one learner will make a short Power Point presentation of the chosen sight in English, accompanied by the Slovenian translation. He or she was supposed present the sight in front of the class. Seniors took over the task very seriously, using the library material and internet search for gaining facts, as well as their English mentor's help of creating the content and ICT mentor's help for creating their Power Point presentations.

The activities lasted the whole school year and they resulted in a small brochure in English and Slovenian, containing all the content presented by the senior learners about the sights they were going to visit. The brochure was printed out and given to each participant prior to the trip to Ireland. In such way, everybody could read about the sights they were going to visit in advance, which made it easier for them to understand Irish guides during their visit of Ireland.

This personal engagement in learning in combination with independent work, only supported by a mentor, as well as creating something meaningful for the everyday use,

made this course very popular and seniors still love to remember that entire school year, not just the amazing trip to Ireland.

Poland: Instytut Badan i Innowacji w Edukacji

Situated learning involves learners in collaborative learning activities (Ochoa, Kopiec, 2019), where they are challenged to use their critical thinking and kinaesthetic abilities. While immersed in the experience, learners reflect on previously held knowledge and by challenging the assumptions of other learners.

Situated learning methodology is used in the language courses delivered by Instytut Badan i Innowacji w Edukacji (INBIE). From 2020 the ERASMUS+ project “English for senior, practicing English with Montessori Method” nr 2020-1-IT02-KA204-079745 has been implemented in Czestochowa Poland in collaboration with Europe For All (Italy), Fundacja Instytut Badań i Innowacji w Edukacji (INBIE), Learnmera Oy (Finlandia), Agrupación de Profesionales para el Desarrollo Internacional (Spain), Osmaniye il Milli Egitim Mudurlugu (Turkey), and Volkshochschule Pforzheim-Enzkreis (Germany).

EnForSe Virtual Corners uses the situated learning and Montessori method to teach the elderly by creating places where they can learn English, experiment with English and participate socially in European cultures. At the same time, the virtual EnForSe Corners, give opportunities for meetings between Seniors who live in different countries and use English to communicate. Due to COVID-19, some activities had to be developed online. Within the project “English for senior, practicing English with Montessori Method” nr 2020-1-IT02-KA204-079745. Cooperation for innovation and the exchange of good practices [EnForSe], staff involved in English teaching were introduced to the Montessori and Situated Learning Method.

ACTIVITIES developed during the project implementation period [01-09-2020 - 30-11-2022] are:

- International meetings to present each partner, bring each own experience to the table, share needs and get involved in the follow up of the creation and implementation of EnForSe Corners.
- Learning Teacher Trainings courses on: Montessori method from basis to evolution, Montessori Method inspired practices.
- Create a EnForSe practical guidelines to teach English to senior using a Montessori inspired method.
- Workshop to define and create all the activities and timesheet for the EnForSe Corner and EnForSe project implementation.
- EnForSe special Room placed in EUROPE FOR ALL location to coordinate all the EnForSe Corners in the partner institutions.

- English corner station called EnForSe Corner will be set up at the headquarters of each partner, where activities will be carried out to put the various organizations in contact with each other.
- EnForSe Day, in which each participant will use English to communicate and share significant new sociality.

Each session have a topic to be discussed / be implemented in the **Virtual EnForSe corner** [<https://meet.google.com/hem-kznr-tcx>]. The idea is to start with Adult education teachers from the partnership to develop some collaborative learning skills, before using the **EnForSe corner** in other institution.

The topics suggested below, can be used for beginner, intermediate and advanced learners! Just choose the questions that are the right level of simplicity or complexity for your adult learners based on their knowledge and their skills.

a. Hobbies

Everybody has hobbies, and everybody loves talking about them. Hobbies could be passions too, you know. Some simple questions to ask include:

- What are your hobbies?
- Why do you like your hobbies so much?
- How often do you do these hobbies?
- How long have you been doing these hobbies, and how did you get started?
- What hobbies did you used to have, but now do not?
- Is it important to have hobbies? Why/why not?

b. Time

As people get older, their perceived value of time increases, so it's a practical topic that everyone has something to say about. You could ask questions like:

- How much free time do you usually have?
- How important is time to you?
- If you had more free time, what would you do?
- "Time is money." Do you agree or disagree? Why?
- How do you feel about time that is wasted?

c. Sleep

As people get older, they start to appreciate a good night's sleep more and more. This topic is often a favourite for all. Some example questions are:

- How much sleep do you usually get?
- Why do some people sleep well while other people do not sleep well?
- What do you do when you have trouble sleeping?
- What time do you usually go to sleep? What time do you usually get up?
- Have you ever slept in a strange place that was not a bed?

d. Music

Everybody loves music and most people feel very strong emotions towards it—especially when it comes to the music that they love (or hate) most. Some simple questions to ask could be:

- What types of music do you like/dislike?
- How do certain kinds of music make you feel?
- What types of music come from your country?
- What's your favourite song/album/artist?
- What music is popular in your country right now?

e. Work

Lots of people work and have lots to say about it. I mean, if you're spending about a third of your waking hours at work, you may have lots to say. Some good questions are:

- What work do/did you do?
- How do/did you like the work?
- What is your dream job?
- What work is common in your city/area/country?
- What is your general view about work? Why?

f. Risk

Everyone feels a certain way about risk. Some are risk-oriented, others are risk-averse. Talking about risks seems to generate some good conversation. You could ask questions like:

- What is your definition of risk?
- Are you a risk taker? Why/why not?
- What are the advantages/disadvantages of taking risks?
- What risks do you come across in your work/life?
- What risks have you taken in your life?

g. Food

Food is possibly the most universal topic of them all and everyone loves to discuss what they eat. This is also an ideal topic for beginners because the vocabulary is usually pretty simple. You could use questions like:

- What is your favourite food? Why?
- What food comes from your country?
- How do you feel when you eat food?
- What foods do you dislike? Why?
- Where do you usually get food from?
- How often do you go to restaurants?
- What is your favourite restaurant? Why?
- What do you usually order at a restaurant?
- What is the restaurant experience like in your country?
- Have you ever worked in a restaurant?
- If you owned a restaurant, what kinds of food would you serve?

h. Cooking

Cooking is another topic that may allow for some good conversation. Most people in most countries do a good amount of cooking. A few good questions could be:

- In your home, who usually cooks?
- How often do you cook?
- How well do you cook? What can you cook well?
- What are the advantages/disadvantages of cooking?
- What food would you like to learn how to cook?

i. Beauty

Beauty is one of those topics that's conventionally more geared toward women than it is to men. However, anyone can appreciate beauty in all its forms, and anyone can recognize the importance of the concept of beauty in our cultures, societies and behaviours. Plus, men might surprise you by caring to chime in on beauty, looks and grooming.

This makes it a good topic to discuss to get some opinions and various views within a group of learners. You could ask questions like:

- What is "beauty"?
- What/who do you consider beautiful?
- What does "inner beauty" mean to you?
- Do you consider artificial beauty (cosmetic surgery) to still be beauty? Why/why not?
- How do you feel about the emphasis that people put on beauty these days?
- What would you tell your children about beauty?

j. Dreams

We all have dreams, sometimes on a nightly basis, and talking about them is a great discussion topic for classes as they inspire learners to be creative and even whimsical. Great questions for this topic include:

- What kinds of dreams do you have?
- What do you think dreams mean?
- How much of your dreams do you remember? Why?
- What is your opinion on premonitions? Are they real?
- What are examples of memorable dreams you have had?

k. Shopping

This one is a personal favourite for many. Shopping is becoming more and more prevalent and brings out some zest in some people. They just love shopping! Others feel strongly the other way—very few people are completely neutral on this topic. A few good questions are:

- Do you enjoy shopping? Why/why not?
- What is your favourite shop? Why?
- In your city, where is a good place to go shopping?

- How do you feel about online shopping?
- How do you think shopping will be like in the future?

I. Movies

Like television, talking about movies is a topic that has something to be said by everybody.

I mean, who doesn't watch movies? A few good questions to be asked could be:

- What was the last movie you saw? How was it?
- What is your favourite movie? Why?
- How are the movies in your country? What are the best ones?
- How often do you watch movies in English?
- If there were a movie about your life, what kind of movie would it be? Why?

In the examples taken from EnForSe VIRTUAL CORNERS GUIDE (<http://enforse.inbie.pl/guide/index.htm>) is easier to discover that situated learning environments place learners in authentic learning situations where they are actively immersed in an activity while using problem-solving (critical thinking) skills. These opportunities involve the learners that replicates their real world situations.

In the end, the situated learning experience should encourage learners to tap their prior knowledge and to challenge others in their community (Stein, 1998).

Spain: Third Age Universities

Spain is one of the pioneering countries in the field of senior education and senior policy. Spain actively participated, together with the United Nations, in the organization of the Second World Assembly on Aging, held in Madrid in 2002, with particular attention to the consequences of an aging population. Later, in 2007, a ministerial conference on the aging of the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE) was held in León, Spain. During this conference, UNECE member countries established criteria to support activities aimed at promoting health, active aging, independent living, participation in society and lifelong learning.

An important role in the process of educating seniors using the methods of, among others, situated learning meet the Universities of the Third Age (UTA). An interesting example of the activity of the UTA is Spain, which officially incorporated the U3A into the national education system, which resulted in the consolidation of education in the U3A with the current trends set by the Ministry of Education.

In Spain, institutions actively developing education using situated learning include:

Instituto Paulo Freire de España

Instituto Paulo Freire de España conducts activities related to informal education, with particular emphasis on adult education, including the method of situated learning. The institute conducts courses and seminars to promote awareness of adult education issues in Spain and publishes on the subject.

Its main objectives are to promote lifelong learning, to promote activities at both institutional and civil society level to raise awareness of adult education, and to create networks between associations and institutions at national and international level.

ACEFIR, Catalan Association for Education, Training and Research

Manages a social initiative that brings together a team of professionals from various fields, whose common goal is to work for education, training and research on youth, adults and the elderly. research related to adolescents, adults and the elderly. Its purposes include:

- developing and initiating activities targeted at these groups in the field of education, training and research;
- sensitizing institutions, media and society to the importance of training and lifelong education
- promoting international cooperation between different cultures;
- and providing support and advice to any other organization active in the same field.

Turkey: situated learning studies

Information is no longer considered to be transferred from the teacher to the student. Learners tend to develop their knowledge through situated learning activities. The term Situated Learning was first proposed by Jean Lave and Etienne Wenger (1991) as a model of learning in a community of practice. Hence, knowledge is co-constructed in a specific context and embedded within a particular social and physical environment. When it comes to foreign language teaching, situated learning can serve as a very effective tool since it enables a setting for real communication and performance.

According to McLellan (1996), the key components of situated learning model are as follows:

- Stories
- Reflection
- Cognitive apprenticeship
- Collaboration
- Coaching
- Multiple practice
- Articulation of learning skills
- Technology

Studies and practices in relation to situated learning in Turkey can be summarized as follows:

Efe, Demiröz, and Akdemir (2011) aimed to investigate the situational learning approach in context with its role and efficiency of teaching spoken language through an experimental study conducted at a school of foreign languages. Results indicated significant differences in favour of the learners who were provided with situated learning opportunities and proved that spoken language can be achieved by authentic sketches which are designed to serve as a situated learning setting

The study conducted by Uz Bilgin (2016) investigated how vocabulary learning, task completion, and contextual vocabulary exploration processes of English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learners can be facilitated in a mobile supported situated learning environment. In five-week period, 25 learners conducted interactive experiments in authentic learning environment with the support of mobile vocabulary learning system. Situated learning environment was found to promote long-term retention, contextual and incidental learning of vocabulary.

The study conducted by Hastürkoğlu (2019) aimed to investigate the Model United Nations (MUN) simulation, which is a situated learning environment and see how it can profitably be applied in undergraduate translator and interpreter pedagogy to help learners achieve deep learning mainly across the meta-cognitive knowledge domain. The study was conducted with university learners and the results indicated strong metacognitive development among learners as well as deep learning achieved through

the active participation in the simulations. The study suggests that the deep learning process can mostly be achieved in environments where learners have the opportunity to involve themselves within their own learning by using metacognitive strategies, which is believed to be achieved through situated learning. The study listed the benefits learners gained from this learning experience as follows:

Learners

- experience actual settings,
- gain a fair knowledge of the tactics of teamwork cooperation and labour division,
- learn a variety of terminologies related to world affairs,
- improve their research, listening, speaking, and note-taking skills,
- adopt formal and legal language, and prepare for upcoming courses
- become aware of their metacognitive knowledge and use it in order to achieve deep learning.

The study conducted by Ünal and Yanpar Yelken (2020) reported on pre-service English language teachers' (PS-ELTs) designing vocabulary learning materials for a web-supported situated learning (SL) environment. Data were collected from 56 PS-ELTs via quantitative measurements (two scales, a vocabulary achievement test) and qualitative measurements (student diary, online messaging logs, open-ended interview form, and focus group interview records). The procedure was found to help participants gain critical thinking, problem-solving, synthesis, and research skills.

Portugal: UTA movement in Portugal

The beginning of the UTA movement in Portugal dates back to 1993, the classes are, like in other countries, scientific in nature and develop a passion for hobbies and tourism. In selected Portuguese UTA you can meet with reading and writing courses for the elderly, as a large group of seniors do not have elementary competences so far.

Associação Nacional de Oficinas de Projectos - Desenvolvimento e Educação

Associations and non-governmental organizations also play an important role in the development of adult education. In particular, ANOP, or the Associação Nacional de Oficinas de Projectos - Desenvolvimento e Educação, which is a non-profit association founded in 1999 by a group of organizations dealing with local development, vocational

training and job creation. It is made up of professionals with experience mainly in the field of adult education and training. Its headquarters are in Santa Maria da Feira, in the northern region of Portugal. ANOP aims to promote local initiatives while providing opportunities for lifelong learning, up-skilling and training, and by encouraging innovation in lifelong learning. lifelong learning, qualification and training activities and encouraging innovation in the field of interinstitutional partnership. in the field of interinstitutional partnership.

ENTRE-SERRAS (Associação de Desenvolvimento do Concelho de Pampilhosa da Serra).

As a non-profit association, it aims to promote the development of the Pampilhosa da Serra region. This goal is achieved through a holistic approach that includes working in a variety of fields. Efforts to foster a culture of partnership culture in education lead to close cooperation between ENTRESERRAS and the local public body for basic adult education - Extensão Educativa de Pampilhosa da Serra. Since its inception, ENTRE-SERRAS has launched a series of initiatives to promote the development of Lifelong Learning and Lifelong Learning; special attention is paid to informal and non-formal education.

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